

MODERN STRATEGIES FOR THE TREATMENT OF BACTERIAL VAGINOSIS

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Abstract: Bacterial vaginosis (BV) is a disorder of the vaginal microflora, resulting from the replacement of normal microbiota with a high concentration of anaerobic bacteria. Given the frequency of BV relapses, the treatment and prevention of disease recurrence is currently an important issue of pharmacotherapy. The ineffectiveness of antimicrobial drugs is due to the incomplete understanding of the pathogenesis of BV, as well as the causes of its recurrence, which affect the effectiveness of treatment. This review reviews the latest information on the pathogenesis of BV, treatment methods and possible strategies to reduce disease recurrence. Currently, new strategies to improve the effectiveness of disease treatment include changing the dose of the drug, the duration of treatment, long-term prophylactic regimens and the use of biofilm-disrupting agents. A number of studies have shown a positive effect of using high-dose suppositories containing metronidazole in combination with an antifungal agent, usually miconazole, which is also useful in mixed bacterial-fungal vaginal infections. In the future, therapy may involve the use of multiple components at once, including antibiotics, combinations of antibiotics, and probiotics.

Keywords: bacterial vaginosis, vaginal microflora, biofilms, treatment, relapse, metronidazole, miconazole, suppositories.

Introduction: Bacterial vaginosis (BV) is a disorder of the vaginal microflora, resulting from the replacement of the normal microbiota with high concentrations of anaerobic bacteria, including *Gardnerella vaginalis*, *Megasphaera* spp., *Atopobium vaginae*, *Dialister* spp., *Mobiluncus* spp., *Sneathia amnii*, *Sneathia* spp., *Porphyromons*. and others [1].

Recurrent BV is now a global problem. The disease itself is not life-threatening, but it is a risk factor for pregnancy complications such as preterm birth, endometritis, sepsis in gynecological practice, including after gynecological operations and abortions, and pelvic abscesses after the insertion of intrauterine devices [2,3]. According to recent meta-analyses, 23–29% of women of reproductive age worldwide have been diagnosed with BV. There are significant differences in the prevalence of the disease by region and ethnicity, with the highest prevalence observed in women from South Asia (28.7%) and the lowest in women from Europe and Central Asia (22.8%) [4].

Risk factors for BV include multiple male and female partners, early sexual debut, lack of contraception, sexually transmitted infection (STI), smoking, alcohol consumption, and frequent vaginal douching. However, there is no evidence that smoking cessation and douching reduce the incidence of BV. Consistent condom use reduces the incidence of BV by 50%, and combined oral contraceptives reduce the incidence by 16% [5-7].

This review explores the latest information on the pathogenesis of BV, treatment options, and possible strategies to reduce disease recurrence.

Although BV is the most common disease in women of reproductive age, its etiology is not fully understood and for many years researchers have put forward various conflicting hypotheses. Available data suggest that BV has a polymicrobial etiology, but *G. vaginalis* is the “primary colonizer” of the vagina and the initiator of biofilm formation [8].

During the development of BV, *Gardnerella* spp., by producing amino acids, provide a favorable environment for the growth of other bacteria associated with BV in the vagina (e.g. *Prevotella bivia* (*P. bivia*) [9]. C. Muzny et al. [10] found that 4 “core bacteria” (i.e., era type I) significantly increase in number 4 days before the onset of the disease, suggesting their role in the onset of BV.

Research methods and materials: The clear link between the development of BV and *Gardnerella* spp. is sometimes considered as direct evidence of a cause-and-effect relationship between the disease. However, the presence of this microorganism does not always lead to the development of BV. In fact, *Gardnerella* spp. is part of the vaginal microbiota of healthy women of any age.

This genus is characterized by phenotypic and genetic diversity [11]. Only certain *Gardnerella* species are pathogenic, while others are natural commensals. Some bacterial species can be virulent only under certain conditions. A. Swidsinski et al. [12] were the first to demonstrate the ability of *Gardnerella* spp. to form biofilms in the vaginal epithelium of women with BV using a specific fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) method. The authors thus elucidated the nature of the main cells, i.e., the cells covered by the biofilm, which are mainly formed by *Gardnerella* spp. The study showed that *G. vaginalis* biofilms can be transmitted between sexual partners. It is known that secondary colonizers, such as *A. vaginae* and *Sneathia* spp., can integrate into the polymicrobial biofilm and induce the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines.

In 2019, M. Vaneechoutte et al. [13] used digital DNA hybridization to sequence 81 sequenced genomes of the genus *Gardnerella* and identified at least 13 groups that could be classified as distinct species within the taxon previously known as *G. vaginalis*. This was a major breakthrough in the study of the genus *G. vaginalis*, leading to a revised description of the aforementioned microorganism and the inclusion of additional *Gardnerella* species, namely *G. leopoldii*, *G. piotii*, and *G. swidsinskii*, for the first time.

E. Turner et al. [14] found that *G. swidsinsky/G. leopoldii* growth was higher in patients with recurrent BV than in patients in remission, and therefore the presence of these species could be considered as a marker for predicting possible future BV relapses. In addition, the authors suggested that high *G. swidsinskii/G. leopoldii* levels directly or indirectly affect the ability of *Lactobacillus* species to restore and maintain normal vaginal microflora after metronidazole therapy. The study also found that the use of boric acid may have an effect on reducing *G. swidsinsky/G. leopoldii* levels and, consequently, the occurrence of relapses.

J. Janda et al. [15] described the differences in *G. vaginalis* based on β -galactosidase, sialidase, and G+C DNA content. The 8 to 17 metabolic biotypes of *G. vaginalis* are distinguished by the presence or absence of the aforementioned enzymes, such as β -galactosidase and lipase, as well as the ability to hydrolyze sodium hippurate and ferment sugars (xylose, arabinose, and galactose) [16].

Results: Molecularly-assisted amplified ribosomal DNA restriction analysis (ARDRA) demonstrated the genotypic diversity of *G. vaginalis*. Three genotypes of *G. vaginalis* have been described, two of which produce sialidase, a hydrolytic enzyme that destroys the mucus barrier. Sialidase is used by some bacteria associated with BV, including *G. vaginalis*, to disrupt and destroy the host's mucosal barrier [17-19].

L. Hardy et al. [20] identified the sialidase A gene in 75% of *G. vaginalis* cases and also demonstrated an association between high levels of the sialidase A gene in *G. vaginalis*, the presence of a *G. vaginalis* biofilm, and the development of BV.

When discussing the vaginal microbiota, it is important to consider the different species of *Lactobacillus*. In 2011, J. Ravel et al. [21] examined 396 women of reproductive age of different ethnic groups (Caucasoid,

Negroid and Mongoloid races) with a normal vaginal biotope and assessed the composition of the microbiome using the molecular method of DNA (RNA) sequencing. The resulting bacterial communities were divided into 5 species: 4 of them were dominated by *L. iners* (34.1%), *L. crispatus* (26.2%), *L. gasseri* (6.2%) and *L. jensenii* (5.3%). The 5th species of the bacterial community consisted of obligate anaerobes that contribute to the production of lactic acid (27%), such as *A. vaginae*, *Prevotella* spp., *Atopobium* spp., *Gardnerella* spp., *Megasphaera* spp., *Aerococcus* spp., *Fingoldia* spp., *Mobil inuncus* spp. et al., in this regard, patients in this group maintained a normal vaginal condition without increasing vaginal pH.

The presence of *Lactobacillus* is traditionally associated with a healthy microbiome, but *L. iners* is more pathogenic and may be implicated in the development and diagnosis of the disease. R. Pramanik et al. [22] reported that *L. crispatus* is the dominant species in the normal vaginal microbiota, while *L. iners* (62.1%) is more common in cases of microbiota disorders. A recent double-blind, placebo-controlled study showed that 11 weeks of metronidazole treatment with *L. crispatus* resulted in a significant reduction in the incidence of BV recurrence compared with placebo (30% vs. 45%, $p = 0.01$). *Lactobacillus* abundance and species diversity, including *L. crispatus*, are reduced in asymptomatic BV. *L. iners* is found only in association with other species of lactobacilli, indicating that they are unable to independently maintain the normal vaginal microflora.

Although the pathogenesis and etiology of BV are still unclear, it is believed that a disturbance of the vaginal microflora alters its environment and causes clinical symptoms such as odor, discharge, itching, burning, as well as an increase in vaginal pH detected during gynecological examination and the presence of cells in the laboratory. However, in 50-75% of cases, BV is asymptomatic, which complicates the diagnosis of the disease and raises even more questions about its etiology. In addition, the diagnosis of BV is complicated by the fact that the vagina is a dynamic ecosystem that naturally changes throughout a woman's life, for example, during different phases of the menstrual cycle, changes in progesterone and estradiol levels, vaginal glycogen content, vaginal pH, and immune status [23-25].

BV has been shown to contain enzymes that reduce the host leukocytes' ability to fight infection, as well as increased synthesis of endotoxins that stimulate the production of cytokines and prostaglandins in the vagina [26].

Furthermore, it is unclear whether BV is associated with de novo formation of polymicrobial biofilms or transmission of polymicrobial biofilms during sexual intercourse.

Due to a lack of understanding of the mechanisms involved in the development of BV, current treatment focuses on alleviating symptoms by reducing the total number of BV-associated bacteria and restoring the normal vaginal microbiota.

In 2018, the International Union Against Sexually Transmitted Infections (IUSTI) and the World Health Organization published guidelines for the treatment of abnormal vaginal discharge. The guidelines recommend first-line treatment for uncomplicated BV with metronidazole 400–500 mg orally twice daily for 5–7 days, metronidazole gel (0.75%) once daily for 5 days, or clindamycin cream (2%) once daily for 7 days. Alternative regimens include 2 g of metronidazole or tinidazole once daily, 1 g of tinidazole for 5 days, 300 mg of clindamycin twice daily for 7 days, or dequalinium chloride 10 mg once daily for 6 days intravaginally. Intravaginal metronidazole is recommended for the treatment of recurrent BV [27].

Approximately 58–88% of patients respond positively within 5 days of treatment with metronidazole or clindamycin. However, the efficacy of metronidazole for 7 days was higher than that for 5 days, but no difference was observed after 21 days (pooled relative risk (RR) 1.01, 95% confidence interval (CI) 0.69–1.46) or 1 month (pooled OR 0.91, 95% CI 0.70–1.18) of therapy [27].

Discussion: In a placebo-controlled study using intravaginal metronidazole gel twice weekly, a significant reduction in the recurrence rate of BV was reported compared with placebo at 16 weeks. OR after 16 and 28 weeks. was 0.43 (95% CI 0.25-0.73) and 0.68 (95% CI 0.49-0.93), with 70% and 39%, 34% and 18% of women free of BV after 16 weeks. and 28 weeks. respectively [28].

Unfortunately, no matter how effective these treatments are, there is a risk of antibiotic resistance. In addition, BV symptoms often recur in 58–76% of women within 12 months. After completing treatment, patients often report a lack of response to treatment and a reluctance to use antibiotics [29–31].

Early studies of the efficacy of antimicrobial agents in acute BV focused on assessing patients immediately after treatment completion, rarely evaluating after 30–35 days. It was soon discovered that the recurrence rate of BV, defined as ≥ 3 episodes per year, was equally high with intravaginal metronidazole and clindamycin [32].

AS Rosca et al. [33] have shown that synergistic interactions occur in polymicrobial biofilms, leading to increased antimicrobial resistance, which explains the increased incidence of relapse episodes. Current knowledge of the etiology of BV does not allow us to definitively determine the cause of BV by the presence of biofilm, but a better understanding of the process of biofilm formation and, more importantly, the role of polymicrobial biofilms in antimicrobial resistance will likely be crucial in developing therapeutic strategies that reduce relapse rates.

Recently, many studies have examined potential alternative treatments, including antiseptics, probiotics and prebiotics, plant-based compounds, and antimicrobial agents that disrupt biofilms. However, despite promising results, most of the agents have not yet been tested in clinical trials.

An alternative to antibiotic therapy is the intravaginal application of 5 ml of lactic acid for 3 days after the end of menstruation for 6 months. For example, in a placebo-controlled study, 88% of women who used lactic acid did not experience a recurrence of BV within 1 year, compared with 10% of women who received placebo [34, 35].

Probiotics are widely used and recommended by physicians worldwide to restore the natural balance of vaginal microflora [36]. Unfortunately, however, modern probiotics often do not contain the required *Lactobacillus* species and have not been validated for safety, quality, or efficacy [37]. A previous Cochrane systematic review found insufficient evidence for or against their use in the treatment of BV [38].

S. Surapeneni et al. [39] studied a regimen of 7 days of oral nitroimidazole with concomitant boric acid for 30 days and subsequent intravaginal metronidazole gel twice weekly. They found a reduction in recurrence rates at 5 months and in 20 of 29 women.

When evaluating the use of boric acid in BV, its additive effects, including bacteriostatic and antifungal activity, should be noted. However, the use of “biofilm disruptors” may provide optimal results when used in combination with antibiotics and may demonstrate antimicrobial synergy. The antimicrobial activity of boric acid does not affect the composition of *Lactobacillus* spp., which are important for maintaining the balance of the normal vaginal microbiota, and it is also well tolerated intravaginally, including long-term use [39].

Currently, there is great interest in the use of astodrim sodium for the treatment of BV (not registered for medical use, clinical trials are ongoing), its mechanism of action is to inhibit the growth of bacteria associated with BV, block their attachment to cells, and suppress the formation and destruction of biofilm. It is available as a mucoadhesive gel and is not systemically absorbed. Astodrim sodium rapidly relieves symptoms such as vaginal odor and abnormal discharge, and its use in the treatment and prevention of BV is supported by high-quality clinical studies showing superior efficacy compared to placebo.

The study of the drug was conducted in the USA and Europe, where sodium astodrimmer was used in the form of an intravaginal gel once daily for 16 weeks. then a break in treatment for another 12 weeks. The degree of clinical improvement on days 9-12 was higher with sodium astodrimmer compared to placebo: 62.5, 74.1, 55.2 and 22.2% for doses of 0.5, 1 and 3% astodrimmer and placebo, respectively. Also, clinical efficacy on days 21-30 after the end of treatment was 28.0, 46.2, 23.3% and 11.5% for doses of 0.5, 1 and 3% astodrimmer and placebo, respectively ($p=0.006$ compared to placebo for 1% gel).

Within 8 weeks. After completion of therapy, the rate of BV recurrence was significantly lower in the astodrimmer group compared with placebo (week 24, 36.1% vs. 45.5%, $p=0.027$)

Conclusion: The above regimen can also be used as maintenance therapy after topical metronidazole treatment of BV. It is important that the drug is safe, well tolerated by patients, does not cause antibiotic resistance, and is not systemically absorbed.

Dequalinium chloride (DQC) is an antimicrobial antiseptic with broad antibacterial and antifungal activity that is widely used in Europe. In clinical trials, DQC has been shown to have clinical efficacy equivalent to clindamycin in the treatment of BV. DQC is recommended for use at a dose of 10 mg daily for 6 days. However, there is no data on the efficacy of the drug as an antirelapse agent [27].

Given the lack of new antimicrobial drugs and treatment regimens, scientists have focused their attention on studying the duration of therapy from 1 week to 2 weeks, but no benefit has been found. Further studies have focused on increasing the dose and concentration of these agents, which have been shown to be effective in the short-term treatment of BV, and then using multiple drugs in a combination and long-term prophylactic regimen.

Several studies have shown that high-dose suppositories containing 500–750 mg of metronidazole, combined with an antifungal agent, usually miconazole, have shown positive effects, including in mixed bacterial–fungal vaginal infections [41–43]. The success rate for BV treatment using this regimen is 93.4% and for vulvovaginal candidiasis is 84.4%.

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